

SOLUTIONS AND PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING THE SOCIO-POLITICAL PROCESSES OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

Masharipov Ikramjon Batirovich

Associate Professor of Tashkent Institute of Finance,
candidate of political science

ikrommasharipov1967@gmail.com

***Annotation.** The article analyzes the development of a free civil society within the framework of the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan, ensuring human rights and freedoms, non-profit organizations, political parties, self-government bodies, based on the principle “the people should not serve government bodies, but government bodies should serve our people”, in as a result of the beginning of a new period of reforms in the country. The author’s comments were formed on the basis of increasing the level of effective cooperation with government bodies of local self-government, developing the socio-political foundations of civil society institutions and ensuring their independence from government bodies, as the legal basis for their improvement in accordance with the requirements of society and the rule of law.*

***Keywords.** Development strategy, free civil society, human rights and freedoms, non-governmental non-commercial organizations, political parties, self-government bodies, state local authorities.*

***Аннотация.** В статье анализируется развитие свободного гражданского общества в рамках стратегии развития нового Узбекистана, обеспечение прав и свобод человека, некоммерческих организаций, политических партий, органов самоуправления, основанное на принципе «народ не должен служить государственным органам, но государственные органы должны служить нашему народу», в результате начала нового периода реформ в стране.*

Комментарии автора формировались на основе повышения уровня эффективного сотрудничества с государственными органами местного самоуправления, развития социально-политические основы институтов гражданского общества и обеспечение их независимости от государственных органов, как правовая основа их совершенствования в соответствии с требованиями общества и правового государства.

Ключевые слова. *Стратегия развития, свободное гражданское общество, права и свободы человека, неправительственные некоммерческие организации, политические партии, органы самоуправления, органы местного самоуправления.*

INTRODUCTION. At the new stage of the reforms implemented in our country, special attention is paid to increasing the social and political activity of the institutions of the civil society. The issue of establishing a fair legal state and a strong civil society is one of the priority goals set before us. In fact, a number of legal documents adopted in recent years created a solid foundation for the free, stable and systematic development of civil society institutions in our country. As a result of the consistent adoption of these documents, the relevant infrastructure - many non-governmental non-profit, public organizations, associations, foundations, trade unions, political parties, print and electronic media, participating as mediators in the relations between individuals, society and the state, helping to realize the social interests of citizens and other institutions of civil society have developed and are improving year by year. In Uzbekistan, non-governmental non-profit organizations (NGOs) began to develop in the manner typical of civil society mainly from 2017. In 2016, as a result of the election of Sh.M. Mirziyoyev as the President of the country and the beginning of a new period of reforms based on the principle that "the people should not serve the state bodies, but the state bodies should serve our people"¹⁷, NGOs and public organizations began to acquire a new meaning and essence, "human - society - state", "New Uzbekistan - social state" as

¹⁷ Speech of Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly. <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/1063.20.09.2017>

a constitutional rule, we are witnessing the further development of the socio-political life of the country with the focus on establishing a people-friendly state, strengthening the protection and social protection of human rights, and fully ensuring the rights and interests of young people. . The strategy for the development of civil society institutions was embodied in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted on February 7, 2017, and a number of decrees and decisions were adopted on the further development of civil society institutions.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-60 of January 28, 2022 "On the New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", dated February 3, 2017, No. PD-4944 "On Measures to Further Improve the Neighborhood Institute", 2018 Decree No. PD-5430 of May 4 "On measures to fundamentally increase the role of civil society institutions in the process of democratic renewal of the country", "Concept of development of civil society in 2021-2025", approved by Decree PD-6181 of March 4, 2021, and 2020 Decision No. PR-4597 of February 12 "On measures to improve the socio-spiritual environment in society, further support the neighborhood institution, and bring the system of work with family and women to a new level", as well as other normative legal documents related to the field in the implementation of the set tasks, tasks were set for identifying socio-political problems in the process of development of civil society institutions in the country, and their implementation is being successfully implemented.

Today, many factors, first of all, many factors such as democratic management system, economic stability, rule of law and human rights in the country, development of civil society institutions, socio-political culture of the population, and high citizenship serve as the basis for every country to have a decent place in the world community and to ensure a decent standard of living for its people.

At this point, the formation and development of a strong civil society remains a priority for every country. Touching on the issue of creating a system capable of meeting the requirements of NGOs and civil society institutions in the country, the

President expressed the following opinion: "It is worth noting that the place and role of non-governmental non-profit organizations in the reforms we are implementing in terms of establishing a free civil society and protecting human rights and freedoms is incomparable. Currently, there are about 10,000 non-governmental non-profit organizations in our country, and more than 30 branches and representative offices of international and foreign non-governmental organizations are operating. In 2017, a separate decree aimed at improving the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations, such as the "Nuroniy" fund, the Youth Union, the Council of Farmers, Farmers and Homeland Owners of Uzbekistan, the Chamber of Commerce and Industry, and the Republican Council for Coordination of the Activities of Self-Governing Bodies and decisions were made, and nowadays the development of social and political life of civil society institutions in our country is improving year by year.

LITERATURE REVIEW. The issue of establishing a fair legal state and a strong civil society is one of the priority goals set before us. In fact, a number of legal documents adopted in recent years created a solid foundation for the free, stable and systematic development of civil society institutions in our country. As a result of the consistent adoption of these documents, the relevant infrastructure - many non-governmental non-profit, public organizations, associations, foundations, trade unions, political parties, print and electronic media, participating as mediators in the relations between individuals, society and the state, helping to realize the social interests of citizens and other institutions of civil society have developed and are improving year by year. The idea of civil society is nothing more than a concept that is complementary to the market and the state. The idea of civil society is an expression of a new radical political concept, which has never denied the latitudes established by the state and the market, but, at the same time, it goes beyond these latitudes. The concept of civil society requires that there be a balance between the family and other organizations that can ensure mutual equality between them, according to the quality of the roles performed by them. An important task of social policy is to create spaces for people at the local level, where state and market

interests are not involved, where people realize their existence as citizens and engage in useful work for themselves and others. At the same time, a certain part of citizens can achieve the social status of entrepreneur. The priority tasks of politicians should be to create, develop and strengthen these areas. In other words, the government quickly becomes a tool for the implementation of social obligations. If the idea of civil society acquires more spiritual and moral characteristics, it will appear as one of the concepts related to the development of human society. On the basis of such views, it is possible to build a prosperous state.

There are three forms of this development:

- the government does not lose its importance - it can be more important than ever - but there is a need to reassess its place in society. State leaders and officials should not oppose citizens' political social activity, but rather support their participation in political processes;
- there is a need for elements of competition in the social life of the society. Let's say that social exchanges can be effective in improving the life of society, increasing the sphere of service to it;
- economy and socialization of various mutual human units is required.

The tendency of civil society to renew the entire human way of life and human labor relations is clearly visible. The society develops as a result of filling the professional and work culture with modern knowledge. However, the concept of civil society requires a balance between the family and other organizations that can ensure mutual equality between them, according to the quality of the roles performed by them. In such a society, men and women have equal opportunities to succeed. The importance of the role of civil society in the democratization of civil society institutions and the activation of community members' participation, the more people learn the norms, values and skills of social and political participation, the more people participate in civil society organizations, as a result, the terms and conditions arise for the functioning of a democratic government and the strengthening of its institutions. In the context of a democratic political regime, civil society organizations prevent the state from adopting laws that conflict with the organized interests of citizens. Public institutions have a positive influence on law-making, as well as by informing the

legislators themselves about the mood of society. At the same time, there are demands for institutions to be efficient, reputable and continuously functioning, always relevant, and in accordance with social needs, traditions or culture of the society.

In general, in countries transitioning from totalitarianism and authoritarianism to democracy, civil society cannot appear in isolation from the state and its organs, as well as from economic and political life, moreover, all of them are parts of a whole.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS. In Uzbekistan, the role and responsibility of judicial bodies and institutions in the issues of improving the quality of public services, systematically providing information about their activities to the public, and providing legal support for the processes of development of social and political foundations of civil society institutions are significantly increasing¹⁸. In the implementation of the unified state policy in the field of providing public services and legal protection of intellectual property, there is a need to rationally use system capabilities, to ensure coordinated activities in these areas, and to form integrated vertical management of existing administrative structures. Today, the idea that "People should not serve for the state agencies, but the state agencies should serve the people" has become the main principle of building a civil society. The trends in the development of civil society institutions are in perfect harmony with the processes of forming the foundations of New Uzbekistan. In this regard, conducting complex and fundamental research covering such factors as the strengthening of the strategic tasks of our country - a democratic state, a free civil society and democratic values - remains one of the urgent tasks facing the scientific community. As the head of our state noted, "in the period until 2030, Uzbekistan is one of our most urgent tasks to further increase the role of parliament and civil society institutions in achieving the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, strengthen the rule of law, and harmonize national legislation and law enforcement practices with international obligations on human rights."¹⁹ Therefore, the unification of all organizations participating in state

¹⁸ Masharipov I.B. Forms and Technologies of Mutual Relations Between the State and Civil Society Institutions International Journal of Development and Public Policy| e-ISSN: 2792-3991 | www.openaccessjournals.eu | Volume: 3 Issue: 3 in March -2023 .52-56.

¹⁹ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. New Uzbekistan strategy. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2021. - 464 p.

administration is considered an important factor in the development of civil society. The United States Agency for International Development, the United Nations Population Fund, the coordinator of OSCE projects in Uzbekistan, the representative office of the German Society for International Cooperation in Uzbekistan, the International Foundation for Electoral Systems (USA), the branch of "Winrock International" (USA) in Uzbekistan, "Умная цивилизация" and "Русский мир" of the Russian Federation " including non-governmental non-commercial organizations. Also, in order to establish close cooperation with foreign non-governmental non-profit organizations similar to the association, foreign associations are identified, their list, database, register of international and foreign organizations accredited in Uzbekistan is being formed.

According to the "State Program for the Implementation of the Strategy of Actions in the Five Priority Areas of the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021", legal frameworks and practical change plans related to the development of social and political foundations of civil society are gaining importance, such as "expanding the scope of implementation of activities on social partnership projects by non-governmental non-profit organizations in the regions, establishing public funds for the support of civil society institutions and non-governmental non-profit organizations under local representative bodies in the regions"²⁰. Also, in accordance with the Actions strategy, the implementation of measures aimed at the organization of "People's Reception Rooms" for reviewing the appeals of individuals and legal entities in each district (city) began to create conditions for building a civil society in the country, to further develop the civil society in the country entered. The modernization of state authorities in the country was focused on the formation of civil society and the rule of law. Because civil society can develop not in a state with a strong executive power, but in the conditions of a modernized legal state. It is known that as the civil society is formed, conditions are formed for officials to conduct their activities based on national interests, social

²⁰ Masharipov I. B. Relevance of civil society in the modern world, attitude and solutions. International Journal of Inclusive and Sustainable Education Volume 2, No 7 | July – 2023.49-53. 6.

stability and people's well-being, which are important for human development. Because, in the conditions of the civil society where the interests of the society and the interests of the individual are combined, the tendency of citizens to join human units based on the rights and interests and to control the authorities and participate in them was formed and grew.

In order to support the implementation of the projects of NGOs and public institutions, the public fund for the support of non-governmental non-profit organizations of Uzbekistan under the association announced grant competitions.

Grant contests were held in 4 directions - "Strengthening the health of the population and promoting a healthy lifestyle", "Supporting youth projects", "Providing social services to the population, their social support and protection" and "Development of non-governmental non-profit organizations". Analytical information on the participation of NGOs in international and local grants was prepared by the association. According to it, 1 thousand 764 NGOs participated in the grant contests held in 2021, 747 of them won. Also, 71 NGOs won international grants. The association has been making relevant proposals to draft laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan and relevant decisions of the President regarding protection of the rights and legal interests of NGOs, and support for their initiatives. It also actively participates in the discussions on the development of draft laws. In order to protect the rights and legal interests of NGOs, to provide them with legal and methodological advice, to provide them with all-round support, and to promptly answer questions related to their activities, the Association "Legal Appeals Group" telegram channel was established. Today, legal and methodological information on legislation is posted on this channel. Legal advice is given to applications received through this network. In general, achieving the effectiveness of the wide-ranging reforms being implemented requires activity and initiative not only from state bodies, but also from non-governmental non-commercial organizations and other institutions of civil society²¹. In the process of civil society development, the mass media will have an important role in fully satisfying the population's need for information, at the same time, in

²¹ Masharipov I.B. Theoretical Foundations of the Development of Modern Civil Society Institutions in a Democratic Legal State. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ECONOMICS, FINANCE AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT ISSN (electronic): 2620-6269/ ISSN (printed): 2615-4021 Vol. 5 No. 6 | Jun 2023 <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJEFSD>.

raising their consciousness, outlook and political culture, and in strengthening the position of citizens. To date, the number of mass media registered in Uzbekistan, especially in 2016-2023, has increased by 41%. If in 2016, 1,514 mass media were registered, by 2023 this indicator will be more than 2,140 mass media. increased by 88% (395 in 2016, 745 in 2023). Their characteristics are different according to the form of ownership, direction, means of information transmission. In recent years, the government has taken some steps to restore contact and establish cooperation with international mass media. For example, the Wall Street Journal correspondents will be allowed to enter the country, a media forum will be organized in Tashkent in June 2017 in cooperation with the OSCE, the Voice of America radio reporter will be accredited, and negotiations will be held with the VVS and Ozodlik radio channels.

CONCLUSION. In Uzbekistan, non-governmental non-profit organizations (NGOs) began to develop in the manner typical of civil society mainly from 2017. In 2016, as a result of the election of Sh.M. Mirziyoyev as the President of the country and the beginning of a new period of reforms based on the principle that "the people should not serve the state bodies, but the state bodies should serve our people", the NGO began to acquire a new meaning and essence. The strategy for the development of civil society institutions was embodied in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted on February 7, 2017, and a number of decrees and decisions were adopted on the further development of civil society institutions. Also, in the implementation of the tasks defined in the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On the New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", No. PD-4944 dated February 3, 2017, "On measures to further improve the neighborhood institution", No. PF-5430 dated May 4, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally increase the role of civil society institutions in the process of democratic renewal of the country", "Concept of Civil Society Development in 2021-2025" approved by Decree PD-6181 of March 4, 2021 and Resolution No. PR-4597 dated February 12, 2020 "On measures to improve the socio-spiritual environment in society, further support the neighborhood institution,

and bring the system of work with family and women to a new level" other normative legal documents related to the field, tasks were defined in connection with the identification of socio-political problems in the process of development of civil society institutions in the country, and their implementation is being successfully implemented. This requires mutual concessions and compromises from the parties. At the moment, achieving such an agreement of interests leads to positive results, that is, to the resolution of conflicts in society, to the activity of all participants in the creative process, and to the strengthening of political and social stability. system, economic stability, rule of law and provision of human rights in the country, development of civil society institutions, socio-political culture of the population, high status of citizenship are the basis of many factors. At this point, the formation and development of a strong civil society remains a priority for every country²².

To realize the desire to build a new Uzbekistan, to create all opportunities for every citizen to develop their potential, to raise a healthy, educated and morally perfect generation, to form a strong economy identified as an important link of global production, to guarantee justice, the rule of law, security and stability in order to ensure, the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy" was adopted by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 "On the "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy" No. PF-158, which reflects five main ideas.

A total of 100 goals, 369 measures, 190 tasks, 306 target indicators and 118 draft normative legal documents were developed within the framework of 5 ideas of "Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy". The following main ideas are reflected in the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy:

- to take a place among countries with higher than average income through stable economic growth;
- organization of the education, medical and social protection system that fully meets the requirements of the population and international standards;
- creation of favorable environmental conditions for the population;

²² Saidov S. Some criteria of civil society development in Uzbekistan. September 16, 2018.

- establishment of a fair and modern state in the service of the people;
- guaranteeing the country's sovereignty and security.

This creates the basis for the comprehensive development of the country. Professor M.Kirgizboyev noted that one of the important tasks is to strengthen the organizational and legal foundations of the modern civil society, to further increase its role in the life of the society²³. In general, if the interpretations of political science of civil society of modern democratic countries are combined, then this society is expressed as follows:

- first of all, it includes non-compulsory, but rather voluntary NGOs in all areas of society;
- human and social institutions in all spheres of society are a complex of mutual relations;
- it is a society protected by legal norms from the effects of interference of state authorities and the formation of independent individuals, NGOs formed by self-selected and non-compulsory individuals.

REFERENCES

1. Speech of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly. <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/1063.20.09.2017>
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. New Uzbekistan strategy. -Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2021.- 464 p.
3. Kirghizboyev M. Civil society: political parties, ideologies, cultures. -T.: Шапк, 1998. -PP.11-12.
4. Masharipov I.B. Forms and Technologies of Mutual Relations Between the State and Civil Society Institutions International Journal of Development and Public Policy| e-ISSN: 2792-3991 | www.openaccessjournals.eu | Volume: 3 Issue: 3 in March -2023 .52-56.

²³ Kirghizboyev M. Civil society: political parties, ideologies, cultures. -T.: East, 1998. -B.11-12.

5. Masharipov I. B. Relevance of civil society in the modern world, attitude and solutions. International Journal of Inclusive and Sustainable Education Volume 2, No 7 | July – 2023.49-53.pp.

6. Masharipov I.B. Theoretical Foundations of the Development of Modern Civil Society Institutions in a Democratic Legal State. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ECONOMICS, FINANCE AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT ISSN (electronic): 2620-6269/ ISSN (printed): 2615-4021 Vol. 5 No. 6 | Jun 2023

<https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJEFSD>

7. Saidov S. Some criteria of civil society development in Uzbekistan. September 16, 2018.

8. Masharipov, I. B. (2023). Governing bodies in the development of civil society: problems and solutions. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 3(6), 1-7.

9. Masharipov, I. B. (2023). Development Factors of Non-Governmental Organizations as Institutions of Civil Society. European Journal of Learning on History and Social Sciences, 1(1), 140-146.

10. Машарипов, И. (2022). Ўзини-ўзи бошқариш органлари-фуқаролик асосий меъзони. Общество и инновации, 3(5), 164-173.

11. Машарипов, И. (2022). ФУҚАРОЛАРНИНГ ЎЗИНИ ЎЗИ БОШҚАРИШ ОРГАНЛАРИ–БАРҚАРОР ЖАМИЯТ КАФОЛАТИ СИФАТИДА. Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования, 1(24), 11-17.

12. Masharipov, I. B. (2018). Transforming Civil Society in Transition Period and Its Certain Issues. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (6).

13. Masharipov, M. B. (2021). Non-governmental non-profit organizations are the main institution of civil society. In Наука сегодня: проблемы и пути решения (pp. 100-101).